

Phenotypic Detection of Inducible Clindamycin Resistance in *Staphylococcus Aureus*: A Study in Central IndiaAnshul Gupta¹, Manoj Sahu², Amit Saxena³, Mansi Gupta⁴, Ronak Jain⁵, Amardeep Singh Rai⁶¹Associate professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Govt. Bundelkhand Medical College, Sagar (M.P)²Assistant Professor, Department of Anesthesia, Govt. Bundelkhand Medical College, Sagar (M.P)³Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, Govt. Bundelkhand Medical College, Sagar (M.P)⁴Demonstrator, Department of Microbiology, Govt. Bundelkhand Medical College, Sagar (M.P)⁵P.G Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Govt. Bundelkhand Medical College, Sagar (M.P)⁶Professor, Department of Microbiology, Govt. Bundelkhand Medical College, Sagar (M.P)

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Emergence of increasing resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus* has renewed the interest in Clindamycin (lincosamide) usage because of its good pharmacokinetic properties in the treatment of *Staphylococcal* infections especially in Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) infections. Erythromycin (macrolide) also used to treat *Staphylococcal* infections but it is a potent inducer of Clindamycin resistance. Combined use of these drugs pose a threat of treatment failure. Phenotypic detection of Erythromycin induced Clindamycin resistance by a simple D- test can be done in clinical laboratories to curb inappropriate use of these drugs in *Staphylococcal* infections including MRSA strains.

Objectives: To find out the burden of Inducible clindamycin resistance & its relation with MRSA.

Materials and Methods: A total of 132 clinical isolates of *S. aureus* between April 2014- June 2014 collected from various Clinical samples were processed to routine antimicrobial Susceptibility test using modified Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method-using Cefoxitin (30µg) disc to detect MRSA. Erythromycin (15µg) & Clindamycin (2µg) disc placed at a distance of 15mm to detect Erythromycin induced Clindamycin resistance by D – test as per CLSI guidelines.

Results: Among 132 isolates, 24(18.18%) isolates showed inducible Clindamycin resistance, out of which 15 were MRSA strains. So percentage of inducible Clindamycin resistance was higher in MRSA (62.5%) as compared to MSSA (37.5%)

Conclusions: For optimum treatment of patients, D-test which is simple and feasible test should be used as routine lab method to detect inducible Clindamycin resistance in *Staphylococci*.

Keywords: Inducible Clindamycin Resistance, MRSA, D-test

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Introduction

The rising prevalence of Methicillin resistance among *Staphylococci* is an increasing problem. [1] This has led to renewed interest in the usage of Macrolide-Lincosamide-Streptogramin B (MLS_B) antibiotics to treat *S. aureus* infections with clindamycin being the preferred agent due to its good pharmacokinetic properties. [2,3] However, widespread use of MLS_B antibiotics has led to rise in the number of *Staphylococcal* strains acquiring resistance to MLS_B antibiotics. [3,4]

This resistance is brought about by two types of mechanisms: Target site modification by *erm* gene and efflux pump mechanism by “*msr A*” gene. Clindamycin resistance in *Staphylococcus* through

target site modification by *erm* gene can be either constitutive (cMLS_B) or inducible (iMLS_B). [1]

In case of constitutive resistance, methylase is always produced, whereas in inducible resistance methylase is produced only in presence of an inducer like Erythromycin. [5,6] Isolates with constitutive resistance show invitro resistance to both Erythromycin and Clindamycin, while inducible resistance shows Erythromycin resistance and appears to be sensitive to Clindamycin in vitro, but in vivo therapy with Clindamycin may select *erm* mutants and leads to treatment failure. [1,5] In case of other mechanism of resistance mediated through *msr A* genes i.e active efflux of these drugs from bacterial cell. They are called as MS phenotypes

showing resistance to Erythromycin and sensitive to Clindamycin invitro, with successful treatment with Clindamycin invivo. [4] Therefore it is important to differentiate these phenotypes. The Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) recommends D-test for detecting inducible resistance phenotypically.

The present study was aimed to find out the burden of *S. aureus* having inducible clindamycin resistance (iMLSB) in our Health care settings (as no data available for this geographical area) using D-test and to ascertain its relationship with Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA).

Materials and Methods

During April 2014 to June 2014, 132 *S.aureus* isolates from various clinical samples like pus or wound swab, throat swab, catheter tip, HVS, aspirates, sputum, blood & body fluids from patients attending People's College of Medical Science and Research Centre, Bhopal were evaluated and included in the study. The isolates were identified as *S. aureus* by conventional methodology. *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 was used as quality control. MRSA detection was done with Cefoxitin (30 µg) disc using Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method as per CLSI guidelines. [7]

The D-test was performed by placing the Erythromycin(15µg) and Clindamycin(2µg) discs adjacent to each other, the distance from edge to edge being 15mm on Muller Hinton agar plate & incubate at 37^oc for 18-24 hours. [5,8]

Following incubation a flattening of the zone (D shaped) around Clindamycin in the area between the discs where both drugs have diffused indicates that the organism has inducible Clindamycin resistance(iMLSB). The interpretation was done only for Erythromycin resistant *S. aureus* strains and all the sensitive strains were excluded.

Results

Out of total 132 *S.aureus* isolates, 88 isolates were Erythromycin resistant. Three different phenotypes of Erythromycin resistant strain were seen in the study in Fig 1,2,3. A total of 24(18.18%) isolates showed inducible Clindamycin resistance and 29(21.96%) isolates showing constitutive Clindamycin resistance, while MS phenotypes are 35(26.51%). These 24 inducible Clindamycin resistant strains isolated from different clinical samples(Table1), 15 were MRSA and 9 were MSSA. Percentage of inducible Clindamycin resistance was higher in MRSA 15(62.5%) as compared to MSSA 9 (37.5%). (3,8) (Fig 4)

Figure 1: D-test Positive (iMLSB Phenotype): Isolates showing resistance to Erythromycin(≤ 13 mm) and sensitive to clindamycin(≥ 21 mm) and showing D shaped zone of inhibition around Clindamycin with the flattening towards Erythromycin.

Figure 2: Constitutive Resistance (cMLS_B Phenotype): Isolates showing resistance to both Erythromycin(≤13mm)and Clindamycin(≤14mm)with circular zone of inhibition around Clindamycin.

Figure 3: D-test Negative (MS Phenotype): Isolates showing resistance to Erythromycin (≤13mm) but susceptible to Clindamycin(≥21mm) and showing circular zone of inhibition around clindamycin.

Table 1: Showing distribution of inducible clindamycin resistant strains in clinical samples

Samples	Inducible Clindamycin resistant strains(n=24)
Pus	11(45.83%)
Urine	5(20.83%)
Blood	3(12.5%)
HVS	2(8.33%)
Catheter Tip	2(8.33%)
Sputum	1(4.16%)

Figure 4 Showing distribution of Erythromycin Resistant Strains in MRSA & MSSA

Discussion

Clindamycin is one of the alternative drug for *Staphylococcal* infections [9] also used in patients allergic to penicillin to treat skin & soft tissue infections. [10] Due to widespread use of MLSB antibiotics, *Staphylococcal* strains have acquired resistance to these antibiotics. Clindamycin resistance can be constitutive(cMLS_B Phenotype) and inducible(iMLS_B Phenotype). erm genes encode enzymes that confer inducible or constitutive resistance to MLS agents via methylation of 23S rRNA thereby reducing binding by MLS agents to the ribosome [5,11] Resistance to Clindamycin is due to erm genes or due to msr A gene. [8,12]

Isolates with inducible Clindamycin resistance shows Erythromycin resistance and Clindamycin sensitivity in vitro, but in vivo, therapy with Clindamycin may select out erm mutants and lead to treatment failure which can be easily detected in lab phenotypically by simple D-test. [1,3,5,8]

The present study shows 88(66.66%) isolates are Erythromycin resistance and D- test was performed in all Erythromycin resistant strains. Inducible Clindamycin resistance found is 18.18% which is in concordance with Gupta V et al, Sireesha et al & Mohanasoundaram K M et al who reported inducible Clindamycin resistance was 18%,18% and 16% respectively in their studies. [13,14,15] Few other studies like Manjunath V et al (57%) shows high inducible Clindamycin resistance. [12]

In this study inducible and constitutive resistance was found to be higher in MRSA as compared to MSSA. [2,5] On the contrary, few studies show higher percentage of inducible clindamycin resistance in MSSA. [16,17] Inducible Clindamycin resistance was higher in pus samples followed by urine, blood samples etc.

Conclusions

For optimum patients care, D-test which is simple and feasible should be used as routine lab method to detect inducible clindamycin resistance in *staphylococci* and its implication as treatment outcome should be detailed out to physician.

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